

Wednesday, November 14, 1973: (Lecture by Dr. L. J. Battan)

[Ed. Note: Wednesday, November 7, 1973, was devoted to an examination, and Friday, November 9, 1973, to a review of the questions on that exam. Monday, November 12, 1973, was a holiday. Therefore, this is the first lecture since Monday, November 5, 1973.]

Dr. Battan: Well, I'm the third chapter in this course. As you know, I'm supposed to cover the area of weather modification, which may be something you never seriously thought about. As a matter of fact, nobody thought very seriously about it until about 20 years ago. Since that time, there has been a lot of attention given to the subject for a wide variety of reasons. I think it would be a good idea, first of all, to talk about some generalities before we get into specifics. I might add that, if you have any questions as we go along, don't hesitate to ask them. And I have a tendency sometimes, when I get wound up, to talk too fast. If I'm going too fast, tell me to slow down.

First of all, what do we mean by "weather modification"? It means changing the weather, it means changing all aspects of the weather, that is to say, perhaps making clouds form, making clouds disappear, or increasing or decreasing rain or snow. I'll bet you might wonder why people want to do these things. We'll cover that in greater detail. You might say, for example, that clearing clouds, clearing fog has important practical applications in aviation. It also would have important practical applications in clearing fog from highways. But the problem there is one where the cost is probably too high for the benefits you get from it, the economics. With aviation, that's not the case at all. In the case of a 747 or even a 707, where there are 150 or 175 people, or even 250 as they carry on some charter flights, the inability to land the airplane can be pretty expensive. I've been on flights where I was supposed to land, for example, in Chicago, and instead I landed in Milwaukee; and it gets to be a hassle. Some of the bags get lost, and people get angry and miss connections. So from the economic point of view and also from the point of view of convenience, it would be very desirable if we could design a system which could clear the fog away from the airport, in order to allow airplanes to land and take off. Now that, to a certain extent, can be done now and to a certain extent is being done. For example, if you've read the history of World War II, you know that England was the place from which most of our aircraft took off for bombing the continent. And they had a terrific fog problem. They developed a scheme of heating the air over runways, to cause fog droplets to evaporate so the aircraft could take off. Well, we'll get into that in greater detail.

The question of rain and snow is one which is essentially obvious. That is to say that, if you look at the problems facing society today, the big problems are food, water and energy. The food and water problems depend upon how much rainfall. I'll come back to that subject later. Now you might ask: "Under what circumstances would you want less rain or snow?" Some are obvious. That is to say, you would like to prevent floods, if you could. Another less obvious one is to decrease snowfall over cities. There has been a lot of work done in the U.S.S.R. which has attempted to reduce the snowfall over Moscow, in order to allow people to get around, in order to reduce the cost of snow clearing.

There is another area of weather modification getting a certain amount of attention today. It's an attempt to affect violent storms, for example, hurricanes. As you probably know, hurricanes do a fantastic amount of damage

every year in many places around the world. Hurricane Camille, which struck the United States a few years ago, did \$1.5 billion worth of damage in the United States alone. And then there are a large number of lives lost. There was a hurricane which hit East Pakistan (now called Bangladesh) in 1970, and the loss of life amounted to at least 250,000 in one day.

So these violent storms affect people and their possessions. And so the question is: Can you do something about it? Can you modify hurricanes? Can you reduce their intensity? And when it comes to hurricanes, you face with hurricanes the kind of problem that sometimes may not bother you. When you read about hurricanes in newspapers or magazines, you usually read about the harmful things they do: the property damage, the loss of life to people and animals. But they also do a great deal of good because they produce rainfall. Take our country. If the hurricanes which hit the southeastern United States didn't come periodically, the average rainfall over the whole southeast part of the United States would be less, and the whole ecology would be different than it is today. As it turns out, with hurricanes we have to concern ourselves with the waves or the storm surge produced by the strong winds. As the hurricane moves in towards land, the strong winds pile up the water, so to speak, so that sweeping over the coastline would be a wave that might be 15-20 feet high. That's what kills most of the people, and that's what does most of the property damage. But the storm then weakens as it moves inland and becomes just an ordinary storm, an ordinary cyclone. It produces rain and does a great deal of good. So the object is, therefore, in terms of seeding hurricanes, to reduce the damage without reducing the benefits. So that's one of the challenges that face us.

There are other violent storms that people have worked on with a little more or less intensity, for example, hail storms. As some of you know who come from the central part of the United States (Eastern Colorado, Kansas, Missouri, Nebraska), hail is a very serious problem to agriculture. It's true of many other parts of the world. Northern Italy has a very serious hail problem. The southern part of the U.S.S.R. has a very serious hail problem. As far as the damage to crops in this country, I believe the estimate comes to something like \$200-300 million per year. The same kind of numbers are cited by the Soviet Union. In our case, the damage is done mostly to grains. In the southern part of the Soviet Union, particularly in countries like Georgia, Moldavia, Armenia, and Azerbaidzhan, they grow a great deal of grapes, a lot of fruits and vegetables. It's hail that does the damage, breaks the plants and knocks off the fruit. In the northern part of Italy, it's also fruits: grapes, peaches, etc. So hail does a tremendous amount of damage in terms of food production in the world. And the question is: Can you do anything about it? Most people think you can. There have been programs in the countries I've mentioned, as well as in Africa. They also have this problem in Africa, in Kenya. The tea growers in Kenya have been working on ways of preventing hail damage. The object of these experiments, the object of these programs, is to study any large hailstones coming down, which might be at least one-half inch or an inch or bigger; they might be as big as oranges. Rather than have these few big stones that come down like missiles, it would be better to produce a lot of tiny ice particles which melt on the way down and make it rain not hail.

Then there are also various other weather problems: for instance, the problem of tornadoes. Well, these are the kinds of things that we'll look at in more detail as we move on.

Weather modification is — at least the people working in the field like to think of it that way — an emerging technology. And as is true of almost all technologies, one runs into the problem: Is it used the right way or is it used the wrong way? That is to say, if you want more rain and I want less rain and somebody seeds the clouds, one of us going to be unhappy, if the seeding has any effect. And as a consequence of this, there's a problem. Many people feel that there are even more problems. This is one area of life where people have rather strong feelings. Some people feel that the weather can take care of itself. Many people feel that the weather is heaven-sent and that manipulating the weather is an irreligious act. And then there are people who just assume: let the weather do what it wants! That is to say that some people like sunshine, and they don't want clouds; and some people like clouds, and they don't want sunshine; and they don't want people meddling with nature. The result, over the past 15 years or so, has been a number of lawsuits which have revolved about these competing interests in the weather.

For example, in Pennsylvania, about 5, 6, or 7 years ago, there was a classic problem which came up a number of times, and it had to do with competing interests in the weather. In a certain part of Pennsylvania, there's a great deal of fruit grown: cherries or apples or something like that — I believe it's cherry trees. Whatever the fruit is, there are very large orchards, and their primary concern is hail. As a consequence, they hired a commercial cloud-seeder to seed the clouds, with the aim of preventing the fall of damaging hail that would damage the fruit trees. Well, it so happened that they retained this fellow at the same time that a major drought struck the whole northeastern part of the United States. And as a consequence thereof, there were very few clouds; and if there are very few clouds, there's going to be very little rain and consequently no hail. So the fruit growers were pleased with their investment because they had very little hail, very little hail damage. Unfortunately, there were some people who were raising cattle. And they wanted H₂O in any form it came. They didn't care if the hail came down in 200-pound blocks, as long as it didn't hit a cow on the head, because the cattle graze, and they needed the water for the grass. Well, when the drought came and there was no rain, no hail, they accused the cloud-seeder for the fruit growers of having produced the drought. It was utterly ridiculous; the drought extended from West Virginia up to Maine. But, nevertheless, the feeling was that the drought was an abnormal situation that coincided with the retention of the cloud-seeder, and they were convinced that the cloud-seeder did it, so they started taking direct action. There were stories that the people were shooting guns at the seeding airplane and were cutting down the fruit trees. And they went to court and sued one another. And the result of it was that the State of Pennsylvania got panicky about the whole business, and they passed some laws controlling cloud seeding, weather modification activities in the State of Pennsylvania.

And now the State law dealing with this subject in Pennsylvania is the most rigid in the entire country. It's very hard to carry out any cloud-seeding operations in the State of Pennsylvania. The law says, for example, that anyone in possession of any instrument which could be used for seeding the clouds is in violation of the law and is subject to immediate arrest. This means that anybody who has got a CO₂ fire extinguisher in his house is breaking the law. And also you have to post a bond of a half million dollars or some huge sum of money to carry out any seeding experiment. People got panicky who should certainly have known better. For example, there was a fellow who was in the State Legislature there. He was very instrumental in passing this law and was interviewed by the *Wall Street Journal*. And he said such things as he knew that cloud seeding uses toxic substances which have

interfered with the fertility of eagles in the State of Pennsylvania. Now I don't know how he established that, but he was one of the leaders in drawing up these laws in Pennsylvania which make it very, very difficult to carry out any kind of weather modification. So this is just an example of the kind of legal and ultimately social problems that can arise because, time and time again, you have these competing interests. One fellow wants rain; and the other fellow doesn't want rain; and unfortunately you can't draw a line — as some cloud-seeders have suggested they could do — and on this side of the line make it rain hard, and on the other side of the line make it rain softly — all the big drops on one side, and all the little drops on the other side. Well, that's nonsense.

Anyhow, those are the kinds of subjects we'll be talking about: the scientific basis for where we stand now in modifying the weather; the social problems that are involved; hopefully the activities in other parts of the world; and where we stand and where we hope to go in the next 5 or 10 years. Some people feel that social problems are going to be the most crucial ones in this area, in the sense that, when people become convinced that somebody back there can change the weather, they're going to start getting quite excited about it.

In the course of this thing, most of the stuff I'll talk about will come out of two little paperbacks that I have written: one called *Cloud Physics and Cloud Seeding*, and the other called *Harvesting the Clouds*. They're in the library, if you want to look at them.

Now, to start from the beginning — actually, when we talk about weather modification, you can well imagine that there are many ways to do it. If you want to really go all the way back, you go back to the aborigine who crawled into a cave. But there are many other things which have been done, some which are obvious things, like building houses and air-conditioning, etc. These are ways of changing the weather within the living environment of human beings or animals, for that matter. There are other ways that aren't quite so obvious. People have built things like shelter belts, rows of trees to cut down on the wind.

Most of the things that I talked about earlier involved intentionally changing the weather, where someone said: I will try to do the following, to make more rain, etc. But there are many ways that you've probably heard about by which people change the weather inadvertently. You know, building cities changes the weather over those areas. It has been alleged, for example, that building reservoirs can change the weather. And that's an idea which you'll hear over and over again.

Here in Arizona, it has been suggested that if you build a big lake out to the west here, you'll increase the water vapor above the lake, and here's Tucson, and the wind blows this way [Ed. Note: towards Tucson]. So you've got a big lake here, and the argument runs that the water will evaporate here [Ed. Note: into the air above the lake], come over here [Ed. Note: move eastward], clouds will form, and it will rain in Tucson.

These kinds of ideas come up over and over again all over the world. One of the arguments used in favor of building Aswan Dam was that the big body of water behind it would increase rainfall. For the most part, there is very little foundation for those arguments. What happens is that this water vapor which comes up here [Ed. Note: moves up from the reservoir to form a cloud; see illustration on the preceding page] doesn't come out of the atmosphere until a long way off.

We talk about residence time. I don't know whether Dr. Schotland mentioned something about the residence time. We have various residence times in the atmosphere for various substances; that's just when it's going to come out. If you talk about the residence time of a water molecule in the air, what you're talking about is, on the average, when a water molecule pops out of the ground, pops out of a lake or something and goes up into the air, how long does it stay there before it falls out. And it turns out it's about 10 days. Which means that, in this case [Ed. Note: illustration on preceding page], since, on the average, every water molecule that comes out of a body of water will be in the atmosphere for 10 days, before it falls out this [Ed. Note: the moisture from the reservoir] will be way, way off there somewhere [Ed. Note: way beyond Tucson].

This notion of residence time is an interesting one. It comes up in many fields. We call it the average residence time in the atmosphere. And this is for H_2O .

Average residence time in atmosphere for H_2O 10 days

You may be curious about how we get that, the way people arrive at a number like that. Obviously, you can't follow molecules around, so how do you know the average residence time is 10 days? The way it's usually done for water is that, for the earth as a whole, the average rainfall is about 40 inches per year, which comes out to be 100 centimeters. There are 2.5 cm in an inch, so that's 100 cm, and that's in a year. So the rainfall per day would be this 100 cm divided by 365 days or roughly .3 cm per day.

$$\frac{\bar{R}}{\text{year}} = 40" = 100 \text{ cm}$$

$$\frac{\bar{R}}{\text{day}} = \frac{100 \text{ cm}}{365 \text{ days}} = 0.3 \text{ cm/day}$$

Then if you look at the air — this is the ground and this is the air going way up — and if you take a column of air to the top of the atmosphere and ask yourself: How much H_2O is there in that column? — that's something called precipitable water.

That is to say, if all the water vapor molecules in this column were squeezed out, what would they amount to? — that's called the precipitable water. And that turns out, on the average, to be 3 centimeters. That is to say, if all the water vapor molecules in a column from the surface of the ground to the top of the atmosphere were squeezed out, on the average, on the earth that would be 3 centimeters deep. So then you divide precipitable water by average rainfall per day.

PW = Precipitable water = 3 cm

\bar{R} = Average rainfall per day = .3 cm/day

$\frac{PW}{\bar{R}}$ = Average residence time in the atmosphere

$$\frac{PW}{\bar{R}} = \frac{3 \text{ cm}}{.3 \text{ cm/day}} = 10 \text{ days}$$

And that's sort of a useful number. It gives you some notion of the turnover time in the atmosphere. It's the kind of number that comes in handy in a lot of things. In studying air pollution, you have the question of what is the turnover time of air pollutants in the atmosphere. It's an important question.

You'll remember that a few years ago, there was something called Earth Day, in April a few years ago. We had an Earth Day, when we were talking about cleaning the air. I think it would be interesting to have a complete Earth Day. As a hypothetical thing, let's assume that one day or one week or sometime next April everybody stayed in bed and nothing happened. You never even got out of bed; you didn't turn on the furnace, you didn't drive your automobile, all the factories were shut down. How long would it take to clean out the entire atmosphere? In this case, you're talking about the residence time not of water vapor, not of H₂O, but the residence time of pollutants, let's say particles in the air. And it turns out that the average residence time in the lower atmosphere of a particle, as I recall, is about 7 days, or something like that. That's how long it takes to clear out the lower atmosphere. So all you do is stay in bed for 7 days. When you wake up, the atmosphere is clean, at least the lower part of the atmosphere, that would be the lowest, let's say, 20,000 feet.

Student: Precipitable water, is that just for one column?

Dr. Battan: Yes, that's a column. That is to say that, if this is the earth, and you have water vapor molecules all over here, if you were to take it all out, it would form over the earth a layer 3 centimeters deep. Now it's just the same whether you take the whole atmosphere or one column. The way it's actually done, when you make the calculation, is you usually take one column; and obviously here's 3 centimeters just like anywhere else.

Now the reason I put this up here is because, in dealing with the atmosphere, sometimes your intuition will lead you astray. That is, the notion of building a lake to increase the rainfall, to me, sounds intuitively sensible. That is to say, if you produce a large body of water, you get evaporation, and it has got to fall somewhere. Why not fall here? The problem is that there are many things dealing with the atmosphere where your intuition tends to lead

you astray, in the sense that you have a tendency to misjudge time, you have a tendency to misjudge distance, and you have a tendency to misjudge energies and masses.

I'll give you another example. There have been many people who talked about techniques of modifying the atmosphere in terms of cleaning up the air. And you say: Why is the air polluted? Why was Tucson polluted over the weekend? You read the story. It was because the air was stable. We had a temperature inversion, those magic words. The air was stable because of (1) a temperature inversion and (2) the fact that the winds were light and variable. As a consequence, the air wasn't going anywhere. It wasn't going up because of the inversion; it wasn't going that way [Ed. Note: horizontally] because of the lack of wind. And consequently, it just collected. And that's the problem, of course, in let's say Los Angeles. They have mountains, and they have a light breeze that blows in towards the mountains. And they have a cap, an inversion. So many people come across with bright ideas on how to clean up the air.

For example, if we draw a sketch of the earth and say the temperature inversion is here, and so the air is polluted down here, people say: Well, why don't we build a big chimney right up through the inversion and pump the air up there? You see, you can have another hole in the inversion here, and bring clean air down. The theory is OK. You can do it. But it takes one hell of a lot of energy! You have to move a lot of air.

And another scheme we've got going in Los Angeles is that some people say: "Well, here's a mountain, and that's one reason this pollutant is here. So let's build a tunnel through here and pump the air over to Arizona." [Ed. Note: Continue to refer to illustration directly above.] Well, that's not a bad idea because we give them our water, and they can give us their dirty air!

But the problem with these schemes is that you have to sit down and ask yourself: How much air do we have to move? Air seems insubstantial because the density of air is very low as compared to water. Water is 1000 times more dense than air at sea level. But nevertheless it [Ed. Note: the density of air] is not zero. And if you move air here [Ed. Note: vertically] or you move air someplace else [Ed. Note: horizontally], it takes energy to move it. And when you look at this problem and say to yourself: How much air do I have to move? and how much power do I need to move it? — you come out with very large numbers. This is typical of problems involving modifying the weather.

Another fellow came up with the idea that he was going to build a sprinkler system over Los Angeles. You know that rain washes out pollutants; so you build a sprinkler system. The fellow even called me on the phone long distance. He asked: "Do you think it will work?" I said: "Sure, it'll work great. But did you think of how much it's going to cost?" And it's enormous; it's absolutely enormous! You would have a tremendous amount of water to move. So the point is that when you deal with the subject of changing the atmosphere, you have to kind of sit down and look at the numbers. And you find out that many things can be done, but they make no sense at all. In terms of weather modification, you have to ask yourself if you're dealing with enormous numbers.

I have some statistics here that I should have passed out. This is a table taken out of a book called *Physical Climatology* by William D. Sellers, who happens to be a member of our faculty. [Ed. Note: At end of this lecture, see "Table 3."] I'm giving you these numbers, but I don't expect anybody to know these things. Nobody ever remembers these numbers, except one of them or something in relation to it. What this table shows is the energy of various types of geophysical systems, in relation to the total energy intercepted by the earth from the sun. The reason for giving the table out is to examine relative amounts of energy. You see that solar energy received from the sun is listed as "1", and the others are factors of that. For example, the melting of average winter snow, the second item on the list, is 10^{-1} or 1/10 of that. Well, as you come down that list to about 10^{-8} , you'll see a number that many people remember very well, and that is the detonation of the Nagasaki bomb in August, 1945. That atomic bomb at Nagasaki was equivalent to 20 kilotons of TNT. By today's standards, it was a small bomb. You know that the Russians have tested megaton bombs, and we've got megaton bombs which make this one look like a dwarf. But, nevertheless, it was a fantastically powerful explosive. And the point is that, if you use that as a standard, you can see that the average summer thunderstorm, which isn't much, has about the same energy as a 20-kiloton bomb. Then you go to the average squall line, which is a line of thunderstorms, and that's 100 times more energetic. And you go a little further up, and you get to the average hurricane, and the average hurricane is 10,000 times more energetic than a 20-kiloton bomb. And so on up the line. You see that the average cyclone, compared to the Nagasaki bomb, is 10^{-3} minus 10^{-8} or 10^5 , that is, 100,000 times more energetic than a 20-kiloton bomb. Now what that suggests is interesting.

I remember that many years ago people talked about modifying hurricanes by putting explosives into them. Why not put in some atomic bombs because that should interfere with the storm? Well, when you look at these numbers and see that the average hurricane has more energy than 10,000 Nagasaki bombs, you could pop Nagasaki bombs into that thing for quite awhile before you would make a dent in the storm. In the meantime, you've made yourself some other problems, like radioactive fallout, which are worse than what you had to begin with.

Now down below that Nagasaki bomb, you'll find certain things which might surprise you. That is to say, that an average tornado is fairly weak. You see, the Nagasaki bomb was equivalent to 20,000 tons of TNT, whereas an average tornado is equivalent to only 20 tons of TNT, which means that a tornado actually is not very energetic. The difference is that the energy of a tornado doesn't amount to very much but the power is very high because it happens in a short period of time. And a lightning stroke, also, doesn't have much energy.

The whole purpose of looking at these numbers is that, in dealing with many of the important weather systems, it does not seem to be practical to try to influence them by competing on a calorie-to-calorie basis. The chances of overpowering the phenomenon, that is, pouring in so much energy that you can hold the power of nature, seems like a hopeless pursuit. If one is going to succeed in modifying the weather, one has to find an instability in the system. In talking earlier about air pollution problems, the question of instability came up. It comes up in many fields of science. In this case, it means that you're looking for an instability whereby a small input of energy can lead to big effects. The classic example of an unstable system is where you have a huge boulder balanced on the side of a hill. If you try to pick it up, you can't do it; but if it's just perfectly balanced, all you've got to do is just lean on it, and it falls over and starts rolling down the hill. So a tiny amount of energy input leads to a very large energy output, especially at the bottom of the hill. And that is the kind of thing for which one has to look, for an efficient system of weather modification. One has to look for a scheme where you have a great deal

of potential energy — and that's what this thing has, potential energy, with the rock balanced on the side of the hill. It's that sort of scheme. Something put that rock up there, and it's got potential energy which is converted to kinetic energy as it rolls down the hill. That's what one wants to look for in weather modification systems, and you'll see as we go through this business that, in most schemes where people have looked at ways to change clouds or change storms or change whatever-you-have, the object is to find some system within the cloud or within the atmosphere where a little nudge leads to a lot of energy coming out. You're not making energy. I mean it isn't a perpetual motion machine, in the sense that you put small amounts of energy in and you somehow multiply the energy. You have potential energy within the system, and it is realized by a small amount of energy input from outside the system.

Virtually all of the weather modification that's going on seriously now — and there is a lot going on all over the world now — deals with the modification of clouds. So I'm going to talk about clouds for awhile.

First of all, I guess Dr. Schotland said a few words about clouds and some of the other people did, too. As far as we're concerned, clouds are collections of small water droplets which form as a result of the condensation of water vapor molecules on condensation nuclei. Have you done these experiments where you have an expansion chamber, Bob, where you expand the chamber and get a cloud in it?

Bob Stout: No.

Dr. Battan: Are you planning on doing that?

Bob Stout: I'm not sure.

Dr. Battan: You did it here once before, when you were trying to show something else, when you were illustrating the change in the boiling point as a function of pressure.

Bob Stout: Right.

Dr. Battan: At any rate, what happens in the atmosphere generally is that the air rises. And as it rises, it moves into regions of lower pressure. This we all know. The pressure is lower, the air goes up, it expands; and as the air expands, it cools off because it has done work. As it cools off, the relative humidity rises because the saturation vapor pressure of the air goes down.

$$RH = \frac{e \text{ (actual vapor pressure)}}{e_s \text{ (saturation vapor pressure)}}$$

This [Ed. Note: e_s] is the saturation vapor pressure, the pressure exerted by all the water molecules which could exist at a particular temperature. This is the relative humidity that the weatherman is always talking about. There are various ways of expressing it. This is one simple way to do it. And as you go to higher altitudes, the temperature decreases. And as the temperature decreases, this [Ed. Note: e_s] decreases. So if this [Ed. Note: e_s] decreases and this [Ed. Note: e] remains the same, then the relative humidity increases.

So that's what happens to the atmosphere. As air rises for some reason or other — suppose it flows over a mountain — it expands, it cools off, the saturation vapor pressure decreases, and the relative humidity increases. And as the

relative humidity increases, it gets more and more humid, and pretty soon you start getting condensation in the atmosphere on nuclei, particles in the air, smog particles, acid particles or whatever they happen to be.

Now you don't need particles. In theory, you do not need particles in order to get cloud droplets. In practice, you do. If this is so, how do you get a water droplet? You get it because these water vapor molecules come in here. You have a nucleus here, you have a particle in the air, and the water vapor molecules come in, and pretty soon you have a layer, and all of a sudden you have a little sea of water, and that's a water droplet. In theory, you don't need a nucleus. But if you didn't have a nucleus, it would require very high saturation. So we won't think about it.

I don't know whether you've seen pictures of cloud droplets, but this is what cloud droplets look like. [Ed. Note: The photograph passed around for inspection by the class appears as Plate I, facing page 66, in *Cloud Physics and Cloud Seeding* by Dr. Louis J. Battan.] And they're pretty small. This picture, for example, shows cloud droplets. And the way you obtain this is by a very simple experimental apparatus, the one that took this picture. You take a microscope slide and you cover it with a thin layer of oil or Vaseline. You fly an airplane through a cloud, and you stick the slide out the window for a fraction of a second, pull it in, and put it under a microscope. The droplets fall on the Vaseline, they sink in, the Vaseline prevents them from evaporating, and you get them under a microscope and take a picture, and that's what you get. But they're small. The biggest cloud droplets in this picture are about 40 microns in diameter. They range in size from a few microns up to 40-50 or 100 microns.

Now to give you some idea of the scale, you'll remember that 1 micron is a millionth of a meter, which is about 0.00004 in., four hundred thousandths of an inch. Now that probably doesn't mean anything to you. It doesn't mean anything to me. If somebody said to me that something was four hundred thousandths of an inch, I'd say: "How big is that?" Well, you want a picture of what it is. As a rule of thumb, a human hair is about 100 microns. The diameter of human hair is 100 microns, roughly - that's for dark hair. The dark hairs are about 100 microns; the light hairs are probably somewhere between 60 and 80 microns. My reason for mentioning this is to give you some feeling, at least it gives me some feeling, for the size. A large cloud droplet is about half the diameter of a human hair, which is why you can't see it. I mean you can't see one. You can see a whole aggregate of them. These are typical cloud droplets, and they form on these nuclei, which are obviously smaller than the cloud droplet. The nuclei which are effective in the atmosphere come from a variety of sources. So condensation nuclei of one kind or another are the foundation on which cloud droplets form. And I have a little diagram in one of these books [Ed. Note: *Cloud Physics and Cloud Seeding* by Dr. Louis J. Battan, p. 11]. If you look at the size of condensation nuclei, they have various sizes.

People who have studied the properties of condensation nuclei have found that they come in a large variety of sizes. And they group them according to some of their properties. And the ones less than about this much [Ed. Note: approximately 0.3 micron] are called Aitken nuclei. Here [Ed. Note: from approximately 0.3 micron to 1.0 micron] they are called large nuclei. And these [Ed. Note: above 1.0 micron] are called giant nuclei; they're pretty small, but they're called "giant" because they're bigger than those. Now these [Ed. Note: nuclei less than 0.3 micron] are called Aitken nuclei because of the way they're measured. They're measured by a device developed by a man named Aitken [Ed. Note: John Aitken, British physicist, 1839-1919] many years ago, and the thing is called an Aitken nuclei counter. They [Ed. Note: the Aitken nuclei] are very small. You need air having very high saturation - very, very humid air - to get condensation down here. You need relative humidities which are greater than 100%.

That's a very unusual state of affairs, to have relative humidities greater than 100%. But it can happen. Now what does it mean? Maybe some of you haven't encountered that situation, haven't encountered the notion of a relative humidity over 100%. If you had a bottle and put water in the bottom of it and a cork in the top and let it sit for awhile, you would start getting water molecules going into the air. And more and more go into the air, and after awhile you get a circumstance where, for every one molecule that goes from water to air, you get one molecule going back, in which case the relative humidity is equal to 100%, and we say that the air is saturated. Now if, for some reason or other, the number of molecules going this way [Ed. Note: from water to air] is greater than the number coming back, the air can become supersaturated, and in that case the relative humidity is greater than 100%.

Now in the atmosphere, that doesn't happen too often. Once in awhile, in a rapidly building cloud, you get slight supersaturation. But in the laboratory, you can get large supersaturation. And the way you do it is with the Aitken nuclei counter. It's something most of you, I'm sure, will have seen one way or another. For example, take a bottle like this one and put water into it and let it sit for awhile. Let's say you put a cork up here, and you have a pump. You pump the air into here [Ed. Note: into the bottle], and you increase the pressure inside the bottle above what the air is outside the bottle. And then you suddenly open this thing, and you get sudden expansion and sudden cooling. And this [Ed. Note: saturation vapor pressure] drops very quickly, and you get very high relative humidity. Well, we'll get back to that on Friday.

TABLE 3

TOTAL ENERGY OF VARIOUS INDIVIDUAL PHENOMENA AND
LOCALIZED PROCESSES IN THE ATMOSPHERE[Rates are relative to total solar energy intercepted
by the earth (3.67×10^{21} cal day⁻¹)]

Solar energy received per day	1
Melting of average winter snow during the spring season	10^{-1}
Monsoon circulation	10^{-2}
World use of energy in 1950	10^{-2}
Strong earthquake	10^{-2}
Average cyclone	10^{-3}
Average hurricane	10^{-4}
Krakatoa explosion of Aug. 26, 1883	10^{-5}
Detonation of "thermonuclear weapon" in April, 1954	10^{-5}
Kinetic energy of the general circulation	10^{-5}
Average squall line	10^{-6}
Average magnetic storm	10^{-7}
Average summer thunderstorm	10^{-8}
Detonation of Nagasaki bomb in August, 1945	10^{-8}
Average earthquake	10^{-9}
Burning of 7,000 tons of coal	10^{-9}
Daily output of Hoover Dam	10^{-9}
Moderate rain (10 mm over Washington, D.C.)	10^{-9}
Average forest fire in the United States, 1952-53	10^{-10}
Average local shower	10^{-10}
Average tornado	10^{-11}
Street lighting on average night in New York City	10^{-11}
Average lightning stroke	10^{-13}
Average dust devil	10^{-15}
Individual gust near the earth's surface	10^{-17}
Meteorite	10^{-18}

Friday, November 16, 1973: (Lecture by Dr. L. J. Battan)

Dr. Battan: Last time we were talking about the question of supersaturation. I think it would be a good idea if you got hold of this book someplace and read it. It will help to put some of these things into more organized form than in the lectures you're getting here. It's called *Cloud Physics and Cloud Seeding*. You don't need to buy it, just borrow it.

Well, we were talking about the subject of saturation and supersaturation. That comes up many times, and there's a lot of confusion about this measuring of humidity in the atmosphere. I was on a radio interview not so long ago, on one of these shows where you talk about the weather and people call in and ask questions. And I happened to have some questions like: "What is relative humidity?" The concept of relative humidity, the concept of humidity in the air, sometimes is confusing. People use the word "moisture." They talk about the moisture in the air. And sometimes they're talking about the water vapor in the air, sometimes they're talking about the liquid in the air, sometimes they're talking about the ice particles in the air. The problem is further compounded by the fact that scientists use various ways to measure the moisture content of a gas. I've been talking about relative humidity because that's the one we hear about most of the time. A typical weather forecast may talk about relative humidity of 20%. As you know, it's the measurement in percent of the quantity of water vapor molecules in the air in relation to the maximum that it can hold when it's saturated.

You'll remember that I had this drawing of the bottle with water in the bottom here.

Saturation
 No. of molecules of water
 vapor going up = no. of
 molecules of water vapor
 going back.

If you put a stopper on it, and a tube that comes out of that, and you close it off and let it sit there, the water stabilizes. The water molecules come out and go back. And if you leave it that way for awhile, when the number of water molecules coming into the water is exactly balanced by the amount coming out, then you have saturation. And if you like, you can measure the number of water molecules per cubic centimeter in the jar. That's a measure of what's called the absolute humidity. Having said that, we'll forget it; we won't use that term any more because very few people use it. But the absolute humidity is the measure of the number of water molecules in a given volume, like a cubic centimeter.

You can also measure the vapor pressure. That's a more useful concept, so that's a phrase which you should retain because it comes up many times, in many ways. And the vapor pressure is just what it says. It's the pressure that would be exerted by the water molecules. If you could somehow, for example, put a gauge in here which would measure the pressure exerted on a plate by the water molecules banging up against the plate, that's the vapor pressure, as opposed to the total pressure, which is the pressure exerted by all the gases in the jar, whether air, which we call oxygen, hydrogen, etc., or whether H₂O molecules. So you can measure the vapor pressure. And the

vapor pressure which I call " e_s " [Ed. Note: saturation vapor pressure] depends only on the temperature. And it increases with the temperature like this.

So if you measure the vapor pressure in this jar as a function of temperature, it increases with temperature. And it's a curve, as this book [Ed. Note: *Cloud Physics and Cloud Seeding*, p. 31 - same as illustration directly above] will show you. So when it's saturated, you have a relative humidity of 100%. This [Ed. Note: illustration above] is saturation.

I also used the term supersaturation. For the benefit of those who may not have been here last time, I'll repeat that there is a term called "supersaturation." And whereas with saturation the relative humidity is 100%, with supersaturation, the relative humidity is greater than 100%.

RH = 100%	Saturated
RH > 100%	Supersaturated

And that's a concept which bothers people. It means simply that there are more water molecules in the air than there would be when the air is saturated. How does that happen? It could happen if you could cool the air very quickly. And one way to do that would be to boost the pressure inside this jar, with a bicycle pump or any other way, and then wait for a few minutes for the air to get equilibrated because if you jack up the pump, it boosts up the pressure here. As we covered in our discussion of adiabatic heating and cooling, if you increase the pressure, it gets warmer. And as it gets warmer, the number of molecules increases. As the temperature goes up, the vapor pressure goes up. And you wait for awhile until it equilibrates. And then you suddenly open the stopcock and let the air shoot out here. This air expands rapidly, it cools off. And as it cools off, the saturation vapor pressure drops off.

So what happens is that when you cool off the temperature to this point [Ed. Note: cool from A to B, illustration at top of next page], although this [Ed. Note: C in illustration at top of next page] is the vapor pressure which would constitute saturation, the amount of vapor pressure in there [Ed. Note: in the bottle] for a very brief instant of time is that [Ed. Note: D in illustration at top of next page], so we end up with a case of supersaturation.

Now in the atmosphere, the time when you get supersaturation has to do with cloud formation. In the atmosphere, what happens is that you get a cloud developing; let's say we have a cloud developing very rapidly. The air is going up and cooling very rapidly. And the air cools as it moves up to higher and higher altitudes. And the air is cooling so that condensation just cannot keep up.

You see, if the air were going up slowly and the air were cooling off, the number of molecules available for condensation would be condensing on these condensation nuclei we talked about, so that we would constantly have 100% relative humidity as we went up. But if the air rises pretty quickly and cools very quickly, it cools so fast that the number of molecules in the atmosphere above that quantity needed for saturating the air is too many to be condensed on the particles; then you have supersaturation.

Well, that's not a particularly crucial point. But there are very few places where you get supersaturation in the atmosphere or anyplace else, unless you get sudden rapid cooling. In clouds, that happens if the clouds develop very rapidly. When you look out in the summertime and see these big white puffy clouds, you know there's supersaturation. And the reason is, of course, that as long as the air is supersaturated, you continue to get condensation of water droplets, and they [Ed. Note: the clouds] get bigger and bigger, and they [Ed. Note: the water droplets] become raindrops or they start to become raindrops.

This whole thing started with the business of condensation nuclei. I had a diagram on the board - no sense in repeating it - well, maybe it is worth putting on again.

This shows the radius of particles in the air. What I pointed out was that these [Ed. Note: below approximately 0.3 micron] are called Aitken nuclei. They are very small. In order for these to have condensation on them, you need supersaturation. So these tiny particles — there are very small ones, like .01 micron — play very little role in the formation of clouds in the atmosphere. Then these [Ed. Note: from approximately 0.3 micron to 1 micron] are called large nuclei. And these [Ed. Note: above 1 micron] are called the giant nuclei.

Now it turns out as you would expect, and we can get you numbers here, that the larger the particle the fewer the number. These [Ed. Note: the large nuclei] occur in concentrations of the order of 100 to 1000 per cubic centimeter. These [Ed. Note: the giant nuclei] might be 10 to 100 per cubic centimeter. The very tiny ones can get huge concentrations. As a matter of fact, as far as the Aitken nuclei, the very tiny ones, are concerned, some measurements have been made. I'll list them here just to give you some kind of idea concerning the occurrence of Aitken nuclei. These measurements were made quite a few years ago. They were made in the city, in the country, and over the ocean. And generally the ocean air is cleanest because there are very few sources of tiny particles. So these are the kinds of measurements they found; these are just averages and are highly variable, of course.

Aitken Nuclei
(Average Measurements)

City	147,000/cm ³
Country	10,000/cm ³
Over the Oceans	1,000/cm ³

These are highly variable. Measurements near a city might run from as low as 10,000 up to 500,000 per cubic centimeter. So the point is that, with these little tiny ones, there are *beaucoup* particles. They play very little role in the formation of clouds, but they're very important in pollution sometimes. Sometimes what happens is that they dew. If you get a large enough quantity of them, they form a haze. Water molecules form on the particles, and they form a haze of many tiny little particles, like you get in the haze condition in Los Angeles. They give the sky a grayish, whitish appearance and cause your eyes to smart a little bit.

But the particles which are important in cloud formation and in rain formation are the large nuclei or the giant nuclei. Now what are the particles. The particles are the kinds of things you might expect them to be. They're a whole spectrum of aerosols. You have all kinds of things: blowing sand, blowing dust, etc. But the ones that are the most crucial in the formation of clouds and rain are the ones that have an affinity for water, the ones that are hygroscopic. These are particles that have an affinity for water, such as salt particles, which come from the ocean. And there are many kinds of salts. The one we think of first, of course, is sodium chloride (NaCl), which comes out of the salt shaker. There's also ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl); this one is more hygroscopic than ordinary table salt. You know how with ordinary table salt, when you get high humidity, it clumps together. Some of the particles develop a thin layer of water on them, and they become fused together. Now it turns out that if the salt is fairly clean sodium chloride (NaCl), ordinary table salt — by "clean", I mean it doesn't have other kinds of salts mixed in — then it requires, as I recall, a relative humidity of 60 or 70% before you start getting condensation.

A Frenchman by the name of Henri Dessens did some work about 40 years or so ago, about 1930. What he did was he captured spiders of a certain variety, and he put them to work making spider webs. That was in the days when you couldn't buy spider webs. As you know, if you want to do anything with spider webs now, you can write to a chemical firm and they'll send you spider webs, just like the department stores send clothes, because there are certain places where they're used for making cross hairs for microscopes. Well, what Dessens did was he used the spider webs to catch salt particles in the atmosphere. If you want to catch small particles, it's very hard to do. I mean the very tiny ones down here [Ed. Note: Aitken nuclei]. It's very hard to catch them because they don't want to go onto anything, they want to follow the air. So the way to catch them is to use a very fine fiber. This room, of course, is full of these things. And if I were to try to catch them by moving across the room with this piece of chalk, like I've just done, very few would hit this piece of chalk. They would go around the piece of chalk. A few would hit it, but not very many. The probability of a nucleus or a particle striking any object, a piece of chalk or any other object, is measured by something called the collection efficiency or the collision efficiency. That is to say, as you sweep this chalk across the air, it sweeps through a certain amount of air. And then, in that amount of air, there are so many nuclei or so many particles. How many strike the chalk? The chalk is very small. The efficiency of collision and collection increases as the fiber gets smaller. So if you have very fine fibers, then you can get particles that are small. And Dessens could. Dessens used this network of spider webs. He dropped the spider and wrapped this thing around the web.

And as the salt comes in, the particles stick on here. When the air is dry, the salt particles are little cubes. And then what happens is you expose these things to humid air, you blow humid air over them, and then water starts condensing on these things, and you get little blobs of water. And if they're big enough, they're called water droplets.

So this is one source of nuclei, salt particles which get into the air from the ocean. And the most efficient way to do that is: You have an ocean surface here. You have a surf that buffets the air around, and you get bubbles of air which come to the surface. And as they come to the surface, they form a thin film which then breaks and throws up at very high speed salt particles of all kinds.

Another type of nuclei which is effective in cloud formation is smoke of various kinds. Smokes contain sulphur and nitrogen, which ultimately become sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) particles and nitric acid (HNO_3) particles; and there are also hydrocarbons.

Well, these are the nuclei that you need. You need nuclei in the atmosphere to get clouds in the first place. That's one of the important ingredients. And the other important ingredient is the one that I've mentioned half a dozen

times, that is, you need humid air. And most clouds in the atmosphere form as air rises and cools off, as it expands. Now the object is to get humid air. And that's one way to get it.

You can also get humid air by cooling the air. And that's the way most fogs form. As you know, we don't get fogs around here, in general, very few anyway, because it's so hot when it's humid. But in most parts of the country, fog is not an unexpected phenomenon. You often see it, for example, in the Middle West, which I'm familiar with, on summer nights. When the sky is clear and the air is humid, you get radiation fogs. Say you're driving along the road, and you have a dip. You drive along the highway and frequently, when you go into a dip, you've got a very thin layer of fog.

It comes about because the air is cooler in the dip. As the air is cooled — it's the old story — the relative humidity goes up. And as long as you get a relative humidity approaching saturation, you're going to get condensation.

Now there are fogs that are formed that way. There are also clouds that are formed as the result of cooling. For example, if you've got warm, moist air over a cold body of water, you've got big fog banks over the water. When warm, humid air comes over a cold body of water, the air loses heat to the water, and the air cools down and produces fog. Fog is a cloud, of course. It may seem different when you're in it, but it's almost the same, not quite.

Those kinds of clouds that form as a result of cooling, either through radiation or through contact with a cool surface, produce very little rain or snow. You get a little bit of a drizzle. People who have lived around the coastline get fogs and get drizzles, tiny particles falling out of the fog. It doesn't produce much rain, but sometimes it gets everything pretty wet.

Most of the rain and snow that fall to the earth fall from clouds which occur as the result of the rising of air. The air rises for a number of reasons. It rises as a result of forced lifting. Presumably, the air may be forced along a mountain barrier. Here's a mountain barrier.

You have a mountain barrier here, and here's the Pacific Ocean. The air blows this way, it rises, clouds form in here, rain or snow falls this way. And what is very common is to have over here [Ed. Note: on the opposite side of the mountain from the ocean] a very dry condition. The prize example is up in the Northwestern part of the United States around Seattle — Washington and Oregon — where along the coastline you have this sort of situation with not heavy rains but a large quantity of rain because it rains often, and then maybe 100 miles inland, it's desert. California is the same way. This [Ed. Note: the dry area] is called the rainshadow. Sometimes you hear the expression "rainshadow," and